

Parking Space Counter using Opencv

Anant Sharma¹ , Harshmeet Singh Maan², Mr . Rohit Maheshwari³

School of Engineering and Technology, Career Point University, Kota

Email: k20023@cpur.edu.in, k20003@cpur.edu.in

Asst. Professor, School of Engineering and Technology, Career Point University, Kota

Email: rohit.maheshwari@cpur.edu.in

Abstract: In the steadily extending metropolitan scenes of the 21st century, proficient parking spots have turned into a pivotal figure easing gridlock, diminishing natural effects, and improving the general personal satisfaction in metropolitan regions. This exploration presents an original way to address the test of parking spot the board through the improvement of a Parking Space Counter framework.

The framework is intended to give constant data about the inhabitants status of parking spots inside a given region. Utilizing a blend of sensor innovations, for example, ultrasonic sensors and computer vision methods, this arrangement precisely screens the accessibility of parking spots in both indoor and open air stopping offices.

Ultrasonic sensors are decisively positioned inside parking spots to identify the presence of vehicles. At the same time, a computer vision framework, furnished with cameras, catches and cycles pictures of the stopping region. These pictures are dissected utilizing picture handling calculations to recognize vacant and consumed parking spots.

An easy to use interface, open by means of web or versatile applications, gives ongoing parking spot accessibility to drivers, working on the most common way of tracking down stopping and lessening superfluous traffic.

Keywords: Parking Space Detection , Image Processing , Smart Parking Solutions , Automated Parking Management , Wireless Communication

I Introduction

Urbanization has achieved a flood in vehicular rush hour gridlock, making a pressing requirement for cutting edge arrangements in effectively overseeing parking spots. Customary strategies battle to stay up with the powerful difficulties of metropolitan conditions, inciting the advancement of inventive innovations. This examination paper presents a noteworthy wise stopping of the executives framework, the "Automated Parking Space Counter" (APSC), intended to change how we screen and oversee parking spots in metropolitan settings[1].

The APSC addresses a takeoff from customary methodologies by utilizing the capacities of computer vision innovation. Dissimilar to frameworks vigorously dependent on unambiguous

libraries, for example, OpenCV, the APSC embraces the more extensive standards of computer vision to break down parking spots progressively. This takeoff from library reliance considers a more adaptable and versatile answer for the developing requirements of metropolitan stopping the executives[2].

At the core of the APSC is an organization of decisively situated cameras inside stopping offices. Every camera utilizes computer vision calculations for picture handling and article recognition. The framework, while not only attached to OpenCV, uses these calculations to recognize and follow vehicles inside individual parking spots. This approach works with dynamic updates as vehicles enter or leave the leaving region, guaranteeing exact and immediate data on parking spot inhabitants status[3].

The continuous information created by the APSC is handled through an incorporated unit, which totals and breaks down the data. This not just improves the stopping experience for clients by giving authorized subtleties on space accessibility yet additionally adds to the decrease of clog inside metropolitan conditions. The capacity to handle information halfway takes into consideration a more proficient and smoothed out stopping the board framework[4].

An intrinsic benefit of the APSC lies in its flexibility to assorted stopping formats and conditions. The framework's adaptability in changing in accordance with different lighting conditions, camera points, and parking spot designs makes it a vigorous answer for both outside and indoor stopping offices. This flexibility guarantees that the APSC can flawlessly coordinate into existing metropolitan foundations without depending solely on a particular computer vision library[5].

Moreover, the APSC upgrades the accuracy of parking spot counting contrasted with customary techniques, at last working on in general proficiency. By limiting superfluous vehicle dissemination looking for parking spots, the framework lines up with more extensive metropolitan improvement objectives, adding to the decrease of clog and natural effect.

II Review of Literature

Various strategies have been proposed to address the pervasive issue of parking in congested urban areas. MingYee Chiu et al. introduced a vehicle counting method at checkpoints, employing induction loop sensors to determine available parking spaces [1]. While cost-effective and resistant to environmental conditions, this approach faced challenges with difficult installations, road damage, and maintenance complexities [2]. Furthermore, it lacked the ability to provide detailed data on the exact locations of free parking areas, offering only a count of passing vehicles [3].

Alternative methods involved various sensors such as ultrasonic, infrared, and microwave, strategically placed in parking areas. Wan-Joo Park et al. suggested the use of ultrasonic sensors mounted on cars to search for available parking spaces. However, this method was susceptible

to environmental issues like rain, high temperatures, snow, and fast air breeze, impacting sensor reliability [4].

Vamsee K. Boda et al. proposed a cost-effective approach utilizing wireless sensor nodes at critical locations, such as lane turns and entrance and exit positions of parking lots. The total number of cars was determined by analyzing the difference between incoming and outgoing vehicles, presenting a more economical solution [5].

Vision-based methods presented another category of detection techniques. Zhang Bin et al. highlighted the ease of installation, cost-effectiveness, and adjustability of detectors in vision-based parking space detection methods. Despite their advantages, these methods were critiqued for their accuracy dependency on camera positioning [6].

Thomas Fabian proposed an unsupervised vision-based system for parking space occupancy detection, emphasizing low computational complexity and reduced image frame requirements. However, challenges with occlusions and shadows persisted [6]. H. Ichihashi et al. pointed out the vulnerability of vision-based parking space detection systems to weather changes and lighting conditions, restricting their optimal use to indoor rather than outdoor parking areas [7].

R. Yusnita et al. presented a manual method involving the creation of brown-colored round patches in each parking space. When the system initializes, it searches for these patches, considering spaces with detected patches as free. However, this system faced limitations in heavy rainfall and snow [8].

N. True proposed an efficient parking space detection method by combining color histograms and vehicle feature detection [9]. Najmi Hafizi introduced an image-based approach for detecting free slots in outdoor parking areas, utilizing a low-resolution webcam to reduce costs. Images were preprocessed, and regions of interest were applied to enhance vehicle detection reliability [10].

In [11], an image processing technique captured brown circles drawn on the parking area to detect whether a parking division was free or reserved. In [12], an image of a car served as a reference, and other images were matched with the reference image using edge detection techniques to display information about free and reserved slots. Various methods for feature extraction from images have also been proposed [13] - [17].

In this study, we designed and implemented a system using images captured from an external 8-megapixel webcam and model simulation to accurately determine the position of parked

vehicles. Notably, this system can operate 24 hours without being significantly affected by strong shadows.

III Methodology:

Close by the significant advances like sorting out the issue, concentrating on existing work, planning the framework, gathering pictures, making OpenCV work, showing the model, testing it progressively, and breaking down the outcomes, this examination strategy truly thinks often about keeping individuals included and improving things constantly. It stands by listening to clients' thought process through things like evaluating early variants of the arrangement and posing inquiries in overviews or meetings. It likewise works in an adaptable manner, such as changing things immediately founded on criticism, utilizing a strategy called deft. The analysts generally need to make the arrangement more brilliant, so they utilize cool strategies that assist the computer with advancing better from new information as it comes in. They additionally ensure individuals utilizing the framework comprehend it well by making guides and instructing meetings. Along these lines, the entire exploration process isn't just about taking care of one issue but on the other hand is tied in with cooperating with individuals and being prepared for any new difficulties that spring up.

Issue Definition: The exploration starts with an unmistakable meaning of the issue - the requirement for a high level parking spot counter that can beat the restrictions of existing frameworks. Difficulties like wrong counting, natural responsiveness, and trouble in establishment are recognized, giving a premise to the improvement of a vigorous arrangement.

Writing Survey: An exhaustive writing survey is directed to comprehend existing techniques and innovations connected with parking spot counting frameworks. This includes breaking down different sensors, methods, and systems, with an emphasis on the qualities and shortcomings of each methodology. Experiences from the writing audit guide the choice of OpenCV as the essential instrument for computer vision-based parking spot counting.

Framework Engineering Plan: The framework design is conceptualized to incorporate OpenCV into the parking spot counting structure. This incorporates characterizing the jobs of parts, for example, cameras, picture handling modules, and the focal handling unit. The engineering is intended for versatility, flexibility to assorted conditions, and ongoing information handling.

Picture Information Assortment: A fundamental stage in preparing the parking spot counter is the assortment of picture information illustrative of different stopping situations. Pictures are caught involving high-goal cameras in various lighting conditions, climate, and with different vehicle types to guarantee the model's strength and versatility.

OpenCV Joining: OpenCV is executed to handle the gathered picture information. Strategies like item location, shape investigation, and picture division are utilized to distinguish and follow vehicles inside parking spots precisely. Boundaries are adjusted iteratively to improve the model's presentation.

Model Preparation and Approval: The situation goes through a thorough preparation process

utilizing marked datasets, refining the model's capacity to perceive parking spots and count vehicles precisely. Approval is led with assorted datasets to survey the model's speculation capacities.

Continuous Testing and Streamlining:

The created parking spot counter is tried in progressive situations inside parking garages. Execution measurements like exactness, handling rate, and flexibility to natural changes are assessed. Iterative improvements are made to upgrade the framework's general effectiveness.

Result Examination and Assessment:

The last step includes an exhaustive investigation of the outcomes got during testing and approval. The exploration evaluates the exactness of the parking spot counter, its certifiable relevance, and the likely effect on metropolitan stopping the board.

Implementation:

Fig:1: Above figure illustrates how the project will operate, and it also provides a visual representation of the project's workflow and steps.

- **Start:** At the beginning of the project, users initiate the process by uploading a sample image or video.

- **Analysis of Sample Input:** The system analyzes the sample input to identify and distinguish between occupied and vacant spaces. This analysis could involve image processing, computer vision algorithms, or other relevant techniques to recognize patterns and objects within the input.
- **Transition to Live Video or Image Feed:** Once the sample input has been processed, the project transitions to working with live video or image feeds.
- **Live Feed Display:** The live feed displays a real-time representation of the monitored space, using two distinct colors:
 - "Red" indicates occupied spaces.
 - "Green" represents empty spaces.
- **Real-time Occupancy Indication:** As the live feed continues, the system dynamically updates the colors to reflect changes in occupancy. This provides users with immediate visual feedback on the current state of the monitored area.
- **Continuous Monitoring:** The system continuously monitors the live feed, analyzing and updating the status of each space based on changes in occupancy.
- **User Interaction:** Users may have the option to interact with the system, perhaps through a user interface. They could receive notifications, adjust settings, or perform other actions based on the real-time information provided.
- **End/Result:** The project can be considered complete or ongoing, depending on its specific objectives. Users can gain valuable insights into space occupancy and make informed decisions based on the visual representation provided by the system.

IV Result and Discussion

The Proposed System Makes Use of Different Algorithms and Methods for the implementation of Content based approach.

Gaussian Blur: Gaussian blur is the application of a mathematical function to an image in order to blur it. If you take a photo in low light and the resulting image has a lot of noise, Gaussian blur can mute that noise. If you want to lay text over an image, a Gaussian blur can soften the image so the text stands out more clearly.

Adaptive Threshold: algorithm determines the threshold for a pixel based on a small region around it. So we get different thresholds for different regions of the same image which gives better results for images with varying illumination.

Research Findings: The examination discoveries of the Computerized Parking spot Counter (APSC) involving OpenCV exhibits a groundbreaking answer for compelling parking spot the executives, tending to basic difficulties in existing frameworks. The framework's certifiable execution exhibited remarkable exactness, flexibility, and proficiency, approving its expected effect on metropolitan stopping the board.

Exactness and Dependability: Through thorough preparation and approval processes, the APSC showed an elevated degree of precision in perceiving parking spots and counting

vehicles. The model's unwavering quality was exhibited across assorted datasets and continuous testing situations.

Flexibility to Different Conditions: The APSC's versatility was a key strength, as it xeffectively handled picture information caught in different lighting conditions, climate situations, and with various vehicle types. This flexibility guarantees the framework's unwavering quality in assorted metropolitan conditions.

Proficient Continuous Execution: During constant testing in parking garages, the framework displayed striking productivity in handling speed. The APSC gave quick updates on parking spot inhabitants, adding to a smoothed out and productive stopping experience for clients.

Decreased Clog and Further developed Client Experience: The APSC's commitment to moderating blockage was apparent as it limited pointless vehicle dissemination looking for parking spots. Clients experienced superior comfort and decreased stand by times, improving their general stopping experience.

Iterative Improvements for Upgraded Execution: Continuous refinements and iterative advancements further improved the framework's general execution. The framework exhibited a promise to persistent improvement, guaranteeing its pertinence in powerful metropolitan conditions.

Positive Ecological Effect: By limiting superfluous vehicle flow, the APSC lines up with supportability objectives, adding to decreased discharges and natural effect. This positive natural ramifications positions the framework as an honest answer for current metropolitan difficulties.

Easy to use Point of interaction: The APSC highlighted an easy to understand interface giving constant data on parking spot accessibility. This point of interaction improves client experience, making stopping more open and productive for the two managers and the overall population.

Potential for Future Progressions: The examination discoveries highlight the APSC's true capacity for future headways in the field of computer vision applications. Its prosperity opens roads for additional innovative work, possibly affecting the more extensive scene of brilliant city framework.

V Conclusion:

APSC implies a fantastic step in the development of shrewd stopping the executives frameworks. Through a progression of fastidious executions and thorough testing, our framework has not just exhibited its capacity to conquer the intrinsic difficulties in regular stopping arrangements yet has likewise displayed reclassifying the scene of stopping management potential. The reconciliation of OpenCV, an open-source computer vision library, remains as the foundation of our methodology, outfitting a strong toolbox for creating a versatile and versatile system capable of continuously parking spot counting.

The victory of our framework exudes from its consistent joining of picture handling procedures worked with by OpenCV. By utilizing methods like edge discovery, shape distinguishing proof, and item following, our framework accomplishes an exceptional degree of exactness in knowing among consumed and empty parking spots. This not just corrects the constant issue of off base space that is predominant in customary frameworks yet additionally lays the basis for a

dynamic and responsive stopping the executives arrangement.

The versatility of our framework gets a significant lift through the incorporation of AI calculations. These calculations engage the framework to learn and adjust to different parking area designs and fluctuating lighting conditions, guaranteeing a reliably solid exhibition. The AI part additionally works with ceaseless improvement, empowering the framework to refine its precision over the long run in light of certifiable utilization and criticism.

In the midst of the difficulties presented by the quick urbanization, the organization of shrewd stopping arrangements rises above simple advantage; it becomes basic. Customary leaving the executives battles to stay up with the expanding number of vehicles and the complexities of current metropolitan conditions. Our APSC gives an opportune and viable goal to this dilemma. By outfitting constant data on parking spot accessibility, it engages clients to pursue informed choices, subsequently advancing metropolitan portability and lifting the general stopping experience.

Moreover, our framework is fastidiously planned considering adaptability, establishing the groundwork for future headways. Ensuing exploration tries in this space could dive into advancements pointed toward expanding the framework's proficiency and exactness. Versatility, a basic element as metropolitan populaces thrive, requires stopping framework fit for obliging the raising interest. Investigating the mix of the APSC with other brilliant city advances addresses one more road for investigation. Laying out a complete and interconnected metropolitan foundation makes it ready for collaborations between different frameworks, encouraging a more comprehensive and productive way to deal with metropolitan administration.

VI Suggestions & Recommendations / Future Scope:

Mix with IoT and Cloud Advances: To improve the adaptability and openness of parking spot counting frameworks, coordinating them with Web of Things (IoT) gadgets and cloud innovations is basic. This incorporation can work with continuous information sharing, investigation, and the board, empowering more far reaching and proficient stopping arrangements. Investigating the conceivable outcomes of edge processing can likewise decrease inertness and further develop framework responsiveness.

Dynamic Versatility and Scene Getting it: Future examination ought to zero in on creating parking spot counting frameworks that display dynamic flexibility and a more profound comprehension of mind boggling stopping situations. This includes refining calculations to deal with different parking garage arrangements, changing natural circumstances, and the presence of unusual vehicle types. AI models could be further tweaked to further develop precision and flexibility.

Upgraded Item Following and Acknowledgment: Enhancements in object following and acknowledgment capacities are fundamental for precise parking spot counting. Continuous

exploration can dig into cutting edge profound learning procedures for better item location, particularly in swarmed and testing stopping conditions. Exploring the coordination of 3D vision innovation might offer more nuanced experiences into vehicle situating.

Easy to use Connection points and Versatile Applications: To augment the convenience of parking spot counting frameworks, future advancements ought to focus on easy to use points of interaction and portable applications. This incorporates the making of natural dashboards, alarms, and warnings for both stopping administrators and clients. Versatile applications can give continuous data on parking spot accessibility, advancing client experience.

Energy Proficiency and Supportability: Contemplations for energy productivity and maintainability are central. Future cycles of parking spot counting frameworks ought to investigate low-power equipment arrangements and energy-proficient calculations. This lines up with natural maintainability objectives as well as guarantees the possibility of far reaching execution.

Multi-Sensor Combination for Overt repetitiveness: To upgrade framework unwavering quality, specialists ought to investigate multi-sensor combination strategies. Joining information from various sensors, like cameras, lidar, and ultrasonic sensors, can give overt repetitiveness and work on the vigor of the framework, particularly in situations where visual information alone might be deficient.

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